

EIT Community New European Bauhaus

FISHART

Programme, Mid-term review

Date: 30 June 2024

project leader: Chiara Certomà (University Sapienza Rome) &
Laura Corazza (University of Turin)
project assistant: Marcello Dato (University of Turin)
project member: Federico Fornaro (Raw-News)"

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PROJECT INSIGHTS

WHAT IS “FISHART: PARTICIPATORY ART FOR THE OCEAN”?

FishArt is a 10-month international project funded by the New European Bauhaus Cross-KIC Connect 2024 written by and granted to Chiara Certoma' (UniTo – now at UniRm1) and led by Laura Corazza (UniTo), in collaboration with Raw-News, Platoon and the fishermen cooperatives of Anzio (Rome, Italy). FishArt promotes a radically participatory art and education process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy. It raises awareness and public acceptance of sustainable behaviours against marine and coastal pollution and promotes the synergic and co-creative transformation of a functional but degraded public space into a place for community life. Building upon the local ecosystem analysis, the wide social network and the results of the recent EU project “SeaPaCS”, FishArt envisages multistakeholder workshops with target groups (fishermen and artists cooperatives) and local stakeholders (administrations, students, associations, migrants, seagoing people, businesses and enterprises, scientists); multidisciplinary (social geography, oceanography, communication) and multi-sectorial (fisherman, artists, businesses) learning sessions; a Living Lab for co-design and realisation of artistic works and a final FishArt Event.

[photo G.Lupinacci/Raw-News for SeaPaCS]

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Participatory Art for environmental sustainability and aesthetic transformation of Anzio Fishermen's Harbour

FishArt aims to support and complement infrastructural requalification processes of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio (50,000 in., 60 km South of Rome, Italy) undertaken by the Local Administration via the realisation of a marine litter collection area. The FishArt participatory aesthetic and cultural transformation of the area is intended to revitalise a public space, functional for the local economy and closely connected with coastal waters, from the current state of dumping and degradation.

The 1km-long Fishermen's Harbour is located in the city centre and is used for the unloading of fishing boats and the retail sale of fish. Although it offers a wonderful walk about the sea, it is not frequented by citizens because of the marine and fishing wastes abandoned on the quay. By request of fishermen cooperatives, galvanised by the success of the EU project "SeaPaCS – Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution" (led by UniTo in Anzio in 2023), FishArt intends to produce participatory cultural and art installations and performances in the Harbour.

The cultural revival of the Harbour is intended as a trigger for collective engagement toward sustainability and a bulwark against abandonment.

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Participatory Art for environmental sustainability and aesthetic transformation of Anzio Fishermen's Harbour

The Fishermen's Harbour is a crucial economic and social area, with many seagoing professionals and business people operating there, as local economy is highly dependent on the sea (fishing, commercial boating, and tourism). Nevertheless the disregard for public goods and space brought a progressive and severe degradation of the area, aggravated by the presence of corruption in the waste management sector. The project offers the opportunity to bootstrap local efforts for a revitalising marine and public culture and connect it at the international level. Moreover, coastal and functional public spaces are often neglected and at risk of vandalization and deterioration.

This is particularly detrimental for both those people who frequent them on a daily basis for their work, such as seagoing professionals, and the citizens at large. Coastal and maritime public space, when derelict, are also characterised by visible pollution which easily reverse into the sea further affecting the already compromised health of our seas and the coastal water. To contrast this trend, target groups involved are innovatively experimenting with the dialogue between fishermen cooperatives and artists societies to fostering a sense of community, attachment and care for the sea and the local

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ACHIEVEMENTS UP TO DATE

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PROJECT ACTIVITY

1. DELX • L.A.D.I. (is) in the Sea! From SeaPaCS to FishArt
2. 01.0? • DEL09 • Feeling the Ocean. Cfp RGS 2024 on co-creative science+art+activism experimentations.
3. 06.02 • DEL01: FishArt kick-off meeting
4. 19.02 • DEL01: FishArt Living Lab: Activity Management [PROJECT DIARY](#)
5. 06.03 • DEL08: FishArt Newsletter Campaigns Web Communication Products
6. 21.03 • DEL05: FishArt_First Collaboratorium #1
7. 12.04 • DEL10: “Plastisphere Explorations. Submarine plots of nature-culture” Geography Night
8. 08.05 • DEL06: FishArt Event: Call for Collaboration & Artwork Creation
9. 10.05 • DEL05: FishArtLiving Lab #1: “Let’s not wage war, let’s fight waste”
10. 11.05 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab #2: Tentacular Thinking Operative Meeting Berlin
11. 13.05 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab: EU NEB COHORT SESSIONS
12. 15.05 • DEL06: PARTICIPATORY ART PROGRAM
13. 21.05 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab: Mentorship program
14. 12.06 • DEL07: FishArt Event: Site Inspection
15. 20.06 • DEL08: FISHART EVENT COMMUNICATION & DESIGN
16. 28.06 • DEL01: MEETINGS & WORK SESSIONS
17. 29.06 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab #3: Participants Meetup on Event Site
18. 30.06 • DEL04: Mid-Term Report

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DEL EXTRA • L.A.D.I. (is) in the Sea! From SeaPaCS to FishArt

On the 4th and 30th of April, and 24th May kids and teachers of the Sailing School organised by the Italian Naval League Anzio operatively kicked off the SeaPaCS spin-off project “L.A.D.I. and the Sea”, anticipated by the inaugural presentation during the final collaboratorium of the SeaPaCS project (LIN) in November 2023,) to monitor plastic debris along the coast of Anzio (Rome, Italy).

The “L.A.D.I. and the Sea” has been supported by the University of Turin – ESOMAS Department and the Italian Naval League of Anzio, in collaboration with dr. Luisa Galgani and Nicola Gaggelli, University of Siena – Chemistry Dep. which will take care of the analysis of the collected sample to determine what kind of plastic are collected in the local sea by producing a short time series of data. Students of the local schools are involved in sampling microplastics using a special self-built sampling network during SeaPaCS, called L.A.D.I. (Low-tech Aquatic Debris Instrument) built by volunteer citizen Giuseppe Certomà and gifted to the LNI for teaching activity and tested in august 2023. A further L.A.D.I. is expected to be built up and offered by of the Rotary Club Costa Neroniana. On the occasion of the starting of the “L.A.D.I. and the Sea”, the sport director of the Italian Naval League Anzio, Federico Fornaro, presented to participating schools the EU NEB project “FishArt. Participatory Art for the ocean at Anzio Fishermen’s Harbour” and invited kids to participate in the planned events. During the day the participatory and open education initiative envisaged from the workplan to engage and collect insights from the youngest

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

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DEL09 • Feeling the Ocean. Cfp RGS 2024 on co-creative science+art+activism experimentations.

More details on the conference, including the open call for papers, are available [here](#).

We invite abstracts for the Royal Geographical Conference 2024 in London on the following session topic. The session is sponsored by the Coastal and Maritime Research Group. The session is co-organised and chaired by Chiara Certoma (University of Rome La Sapienza), Federico Fornaro (Raw-News), Stefania Benetti (University of Eastern Piedmont), Antonella Passani (T6-Ecosystem)

The session focuses on how the combination of science, art and participatory processes can contribute to exploring and establishing a connection between society and the ocean. Our interest goes to transectorial and transdisciplinary-inspired artistic and creative processes promoted by scientists, artists, activists, seagoing people and ocean-lovers that experiment with new forms of investigation and expression to explore to motivate, trigger and support our commitments toward ocean challenges. Particularly we focus on participatory or collaborative artistic and creative processes on the belief that that engagement can bring about a deeper understanding and commitment of society with ocean hazards and challenges, not only via cultural consumption, but also in experimenting with artistic/performing arts themselves.

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

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DEL01 • FishArt kick-off meeting

The kick-off meeting of the of the EU NEB FishArt project is held on the 26th of February at the Municipality of Anzio, Rome (Italy) with representatives of the administration and the Capitaneria di Porto.

FishArt promotes a radically participatory art and education process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy.

During the kick-off meeting with dr. Monaco, Anzio City Council and mar. Costabile, Capitaneria di Porto, the project inspiration, the programme and the logistic details have been discussed. [FULL ARTICLE](#)

The project presentation by Chiara Certomà is available [here](#)

DEL01 • FishArt Living Lab: Activity Management

06.02.2024 Project set-up meeting with NEB project officer FishArt team with UniTo secretary and NEB PO (Ellen Gale)

19.02.2024 Operative meeting FishArt team

26.02.2024 FishArt Kick-off meeting with local administration (Eugenio Monaco) and harbour institution (Massimo Costabile)

05.04.2024 Starting of the mentorship programme with NEB PO (Ellen Gale) and Vanessa Gerotto

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DEL05 #1 • FishArt_First Collaboratorium

On March 21, 2024, the first public FishArt collaboratorium is held at the Italian Naval League in Anzio (Rome, Italy) with local stakeholders at 6 pm. Promoters Chiara Certomà (University of Turin and Rome Sapienza), Federico Fornaro, director of the international video documentation company Raw-News and Marcello Dato connected from Berlin for the international artistic promotion company Platoon welcomed the participants and presented the activities envisaged by the FishArt project aimed at supporting the sustainable redevelopment process of the port area of Anzio undertaken by the Local Administration. Through the active participation of all components of the local population, and in connection with international experiences and experts, co-education initiatives will be implemented for the protection of the ocean from pollution and the revitalization of public space with artistic and creative events.

Participants were invited to participate in the planned events, in particular the first co-education event “Non Facciamo la guerra, Combattiamo i Rifiuti”(2 May 2024) organized by Municipality of Anzio in collaboration with the FishArt project, the FishArt Living Lab meeting (May-June) for the collective planning of the FishArt Event (July) which involves the creation, implementation and installation in the port areas for the Ocean of moments creative and artistic works (about which invitations and information will be sent in time).

Furthermore at the end of the collaboratorium, the DUWO boxes, washable and reusable, are delivered to the captains of the remaining 10 fishing boats of the “Concordia” and “Fanciulla d’Anzio” Cooperative of Anzio-Roma at the Innocenziano Pier, after the European project “SeaPaCS. Citizen-Scientist against plastic in the sea”. (<https://crowdusg.net/seapacs/>).

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

[VIDEO REPORT](#) (Long Version)

[cover photo G.Lupinacci]

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ARTE PARTECIPATIVA PER L'OCEANO

21 MAR • 6pm

FISHART CO-LABORATORIO

LEGA NAVALE ITALIANA DI ANZIO

Riviera Zanardelli 28 Anzio - Roma

Photo: Giuseppe Lupinacci / Raw-News

DEL08 • FishArt Newsletter Campaigns

<input type="checkbox"/>	FISHART LIVING LAB MEETUP (copy 01) ✉ Email standard Ultima modifica effettuata in data mer 19 giu, 19:05 da Marcello Dato	Inviata mer 19 giu, 19:05	FISHART Tags: PARTICIPANTS 10 destinatari	100.0% Aperture	30.0% Clic
<input type="checkbox"/>	FISHART LIVING LAB MEETUP ✉ Email standard Ultima modifica effettuata in data dom 09 giu, 05:12 da Marcello Dato	Inviata dom 09 giu, 05:12	FISHART Tags: STAMPA 27 destinatari	40.7% Aperture	0.0% Clic
<input type="checkbox"/>	VIDEO REPORT• 10 MAGGIO 2024: “Non Facciamo la guerra,Combattiamo i Rifiuti” ✉ Email standard Ultima modifica effettuata in data lun 20 mag, 15:28 da Marcello Dato	Inviata lun 20 mag, 15:28	FISHART 203 destinatari	51.8% Aperture	6.1% Clic
<input type="checkbox"/>	REPORT• 10 MAGGIO 2024: “Non Facciamo la guerra,Combattiamo i Rifiuti” ✉ Email standard Ultima modifica effettuata in data dom 12 mag, 18:34 da Marcello Dato	Inviata dom 12 mag, 18:34	FISHART 167 destinatari	52.4% Aperture	11.0% Clic
<input type="checkbox"/>	CALL FOR PROPOSALS: FISHART EVENT 2024 ✉ Email standard Ultima modifica effettuata in data gio 09 mag, 02:52 da Marcello Dato	Inviata gio 09 mag, 02:52	FISHART 167 destinatari	52.4% Aperture	5.5% Clic
<input type="checkbox"/>	NON FACCIAMO LA GUERRA, COMBATTIAMO I RIFIUTI (copy 02) ✉ Email standard Ultima modifica effettuata in data ven 03 mag, 01:13 da Marcello Dato	Inviata ven 03 mag, 01:13	FISHART 169 destinatari	50.3% Aperture	1.2% Clic

[CO-LABORATORIUM #1 INVITATION](#)

[CO-LABORATORIUM #1 REPORT](#)

[CO-LABORATORIUM #1 VIDEO REPORT](#)

[OPEN CALL FOR ARTWORK CREATION](#)

[LIVING LAB #2 CALL TO ACTION](#)

[LIVING LAB #2 REPORT](#)

[LIVING LAB #2 VIDEO REPORT](#)

[LIVING LAB #3](#)

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DEL08 • Web Communication Products

Communication channels opened on Instagram, YouTube and Project Homepage:

<https://www.instagram.com/fisharteu/>

<https://www.youtube.com/@FISHARTEU>

<https://crowdusg.net/fishart/>

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DEL05 • FishArt Living Lab #1: Planning & Production

01.04-02.025.2024 Living Lab activity #1:
coordination, logistical and technical organization, networking, institutional requirements and realisation of the community plogging event by Raw-News, Raw-Drivers and Platoon with Municipal Administration (Environment and Education departments), 4 local primary and secondary schools (about 250 kids), Legambiente association.

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DEL10 • “Plastisphere Explorations. Submarine plots of nature-culture” Geography Night

[photo: G. Lupinacci]

The International Night of Geography 2024 organized by La Sapienza University at the Botanical Garden of Rome, Largo Cristina di Sweden 23 A, from 8pm to 11pm the underwater photography exhibition “Explorations of the Plastisphere. Underwater plots of nature-culture” will be exhibited by photographer Giuseppe Lupinacci in collaboration with the British video-documentation agency Raw-News.

The exhibition presents the culmination of a collaborative research and documentation process aimed at making visible and reconceptualizing the presence of plastic in the oceans as an integral part of marine ecosystems.

The professional photographic documentation process was conducted in close connection with scholars of social geography and oceanography during the EU Horizon pilot project “SeaPaCS. Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution” (2023) and the EU-Culture Moves Europe project “Tentacular Thinking. Experiencing underwater assemblages of culture and nature” (2024), both led by Chiara Certomà (La Sapienza University of Rome).

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

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DEL05 #2 • FishArt: “Let’s not wage war, let’s fight waste”

As part of the FishArt project agenda, transect walks and educational training initiatives have been combined in a major event, strongly requested by the local community. The synergy between local institutions and international research aims to stimulate civic participation on the problem of marine pollution and the care of the coastal territory. The event “Let’s not make war, let’s fight waste!” is a civic initiative promoted by the Extraordinary Commission supported by the Environment Area of the Municipality of Anzio which aims to involve all the components of civil society for a collaborative cleaning of the beaches, transforming the celebrations of the Anzio/Nettuno landing into a moment of sharing and to raise awareness against marine pollution. On the occasion of the celebration of the 80th anniversary of the Anzio landing, volunteers and activists will be engaged in “community plogging” (community cleanup) at the Lido dei Gigli public beach.

The initiative is organized by the European project New European Bauhaus “FishArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean at the Port of Anzio” led by the University of Turin and Sapienza University of Rome together with “Raw-News”, “PLATOON Cultural Development”, “Raw-Drivers” and with the support of the club Legambiente “Le Rondini” Anzio-Nettuno, in collaboration with the Extraordinary Commission supported by the Environment Area of the Municipality of Anzio. Federico Fornaro (Raw-News) took the lead in coordinating the logistic and the technical realisation. Press release available [here](#):

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

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ARTE PARTECIPATIVA PER L'OCEANO

10 MAGGIO 2024 • 9:30 - 12:30 Lido dei Gigli
**NON FACCIAMO LA GUERRA
COMBATTIAMO I
RIFIUTI!**

Del Dipartimento di Economia di Anzio

Città di Anzio
Municipalità di Anzio - Roma

DIPARTIMENTO DI METODI E MODELLI
PER L'ECONOMIA E IL TERRITORIO E LA FINANZA
MEMORIE

SAPIENZA
Università di Roma

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DEL06 • FishArtEvent: Call for Collaboration & Artwork Creation

The EU NEB FishArt project invites creative citizens, innovators, activists, artists and change-makers individually or in associations (formal and informal), foundations, companies and institutions to propose initiatives to be implemented during the FishArt Event on 27 July 2024, from 6pm to 10pm at the Port of Anzio, Rome (Italy). The initiative is organized in collaboration with the European New European Bauhaus project “FishArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean at the Port of Anzio” led by the University of Turin and Sapienza University of Rome in collaboration with “Raw-News”, “PLATOON Cultural Development”, “Rawdrivers.org”. The FishArt Event is an evening of collaborative experimentation and participatory art for the Ocean to support the redevelopment process of a vital public space for the city of Anzio, the Porto dei Anzio. The event will be held at the Molo Innocenziano. The active and creative participation of citizens is fundamental in order to best organize the event, and the FishArt team will avail itself of the advice of an international Scientific Committee which will consider all the proposals received. The synergy between local institutions and international research aims to stimulate civic participation on the problem of marine pollution and the care of the coastal territory. All Images: Rawdrivers.org

The EU NEB FishArt project invites creative citizens, innovators, activists, artists and change-makers individually or in associations (formal and informal), foundations, companies and institutions to propose initiatives to be implemented during the FishArt Event on 27 July 2024, from 6pm to 10pm at the Port of Anzio, Rome (Italy). The initiative is organized in collaboration with the European New European Bauhaus project “FishArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean at the Port of Anzio” led by the University of Turin and Sapienza University of Rome in collaboration with “Raw-News”, “PLATOON Cultural Development”, “Rawdrivers.org”.

The FishArt Event is an evening of collaborative experimentation and participatory art for the Ocean to support the redevelopment process of a vital public space for the city of Anzio, the Porto dei Anzio. The event will be held at the Molo Innocenziano. The active and creative participation of citizens is fundamental in order to best organize the event, and the FishArt team will avail itself of the advice of an international Scientific Committee which will consider all the proposals received. The synergy between local institutions and international research aims to stimulate civic participation on the problem of marine pollution and the care of the coastal territory.

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DEL05 • FishArt EU NEB COHORT SESSIONS

FishArt
Chiara Certoma'
What you do without using your job title!

Anzio, Italy

1 FishArt participatory process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy.

2 FishArt aims to support and complement infrastructural requalification processes of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio (50,000 in., 60 km South of Rome, Italy) undertaken by the Local Administration via the realisation of a marine litter collection area. The FishArt participatory aesthetic and cultural transformation of the area is intended to revitalise a public space, functional for the local economy and closely connected with coastal waters, from the current state of dumping and degradation.

3 Fishermen, creative/ artistic communities

4 Building upon the local ecosystem analysis, the wide social network and the results of the recent EU project "SeaPaCS", FishArt envisages multistakeholder workshops with target groups (fishermen and artists cooperatives) and local stakeholders (administrations, students, associations, migrants, seagoing people, businesses and enterprises, scientists); multidisciplinary (social geography, oceanography, communication) and multi-sectorial (fisherman, artists, businesses) learning sessions; a Living Lab for co-design and realisation of artistic works and a final FishArt Event.

<https://crowdusg.net/fishart/>
fisharteu@gmail.com
chiara.certoma

May 2024: Remotely taking part in the EU NEB cohort session

<https://www.climate-kic.org/news/16-community-focused-projects-receive-new-european-bauhaus-funding>

DEL05 • FishArt LIVING LAB #2 Operative Meeting Berlin

16.05.2024 FishArt operative meeting with PLATOON and Raw-News companies in Berlin to discuss the broader impact of the project, meet creatives, and get inspired by Berlin's creative scene.

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DEL05 • FishArt Living Lab: Mentorship program

21.05.2024 Meeting of the mentorship programme with [Oleg Koefoed](#) and [Vanessa Gerotto](#)

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DEL07 • FishArt Event: Production meeting

03.06.2024 Operative meeting for preparing the in-person Living Lab with Fishermen and creatives

DEL07 • FishArt Event: Site Inspection

[photo M.Dato]

12.06.2024 Technical inspection by the FishArt team at Molo Innocenziano for FishArt Event preparation.

DEL07 • EVENT LOCATION SITE INSPECTION

DEL05 • FishArt Living Lab #2: Design Collaborative Process

29.04.2024 -30.05.2024 Living Lab activity #2: design of the collaborative art process (involving stakeholders) and preparation of artworks.

DEL05 #3 • FishArt Living Lab: Participants Meetup on Event Site

[image rawdrivers.org]

The FishArt Living Lab is held on the 29th June, in preparation for the FishArt Event on July 27th. This meeting is aimed at all of you who responded enthusiastically to our Call To Action by sending proposals and to the fishermen and representatives of local institutions.

Date: June 29, 2024

Time: 6pm

Location: Molo Innocenziano (in front of the hydrofoil boarding point) MAP

Purpose: Organization of the FishArt Event on July 27th

Meeting Program:

- Presentation of the FISHART LIVING LAB Event Programme
- FishArt Museum of Marine Pollution: We will discuss how to set up nets from fishing for the Marine Trash Museum and the Fresh Trash Market performance.
- Presentation of the Projects Selected by the scientific commission.
- Organization of workshops, creative laboratories and project arrangement.

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

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DELO5 • LIVING LAB #3: PARTICIPANTS MEETUP AT CULTURE SEAPORT

DEL11 • Stakeholder Report

outputs and outcomes, potential impact, conclusions and evidence of the KPIs.

Stakeholders at Anzio Seaport: A Brief Insight & Analytical Report

Introduction

Anzio Seaport, with its rich maritime history and cultural heritage, is a hub of various stakeholders, each contributing uniquely to its dynamic environment. This report provides a detailed analysis of the stakeholders at Anzio Seaport, their connections, and the essential nature of their collaboration. Special emphasis is placed on finding strategies to engage the younger generation with professions related to maritime culture and developing an ecological consciousness.

Fishermen and Maritime Workers

Angelo Grillo, President of the Fishermen's Union, represents the interests of local fishermen, mostly long-range Trawling Fishing. He was present at the first Collaboratorium and helped us liaise with different fishermen. Through him we met **Manuele** while he was repairing a fishing net. A veteran fisherman who shared with us historical anecdotes about biologists visiting every four years to study nanoplastics in fish brains, which he believes originate from household washing machines and textile discharges. **Marcello Audace**, a long-range trawling captain, has provided us with fishing nets for the event and various forms of support, playing a crucial role in the operational aspects and setup of the FishArt Porto Cultura. The **Corto Raggio** (short-range) fishermen, **Simone and Fulvio** from the fishing boat Perditempo 3, are innovators working on a new sea-cleaning project that incorporates live streaming and a civic observatory for citizen science.

Their work exemplifies the blend of traditional practices and modern technology. **Gianluca**, a young captain, symbolizes the generational shift in maritime professions. He relies heavily on technology but faces criticism from the older guard for lacking practical decision-making skills essential in risky situations.

Challenges and Required Solutions

A sense of belonging and recognition is vital for the community. One pressing issue is the decommissioning of the community-led oil tank initiative without a replacement. Additionally, the **strabordo attracco**—a ready-made docking solution—remains unused due to restrictions imposed by the Capitaneria di Porto. **Ecological islands** to recycle and dispose of marine plastics and trash found at sea, a solution desired by all stakeholders, face coordination challenges. All stakeholders have started working together for a common cause, and although they hold different opinions and motivations, they are pushing in the same direction.

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DEL11 • Stakeholder Report

Key Collaborators and Support Systems

LEGAMBIENTE has been the most supportive association and it really helped having them on board as collaborator, they bring along a long term reputation which gave us an edge with other institutions. At the seaport we had few good tips from **Marco Palomba**, a connector within the cooperative for fish auctions, provides essential water supplies and connects the team with behind-the-scenes workers at the seaport. The **Cantiere Navale**, represented by **Gianpaolo Gallinari Maestro d'Ascia**, a master boat builder, highlights the declining client base and reputation of Anzio's naval yards. Investing in marine trades and excellence is critical for attracting newcomers. Despite financial struggles, Maestro d'Ascia supported the event with high-voltage electricity.

Lega Navale Italiana, the association secretary **Francesca**, emphasizes the need for enthusiastic teenagers to discover sailing and sea culture. Numbers are declining every year.. Many local young people lack interest in learning how to sail, which is a significant concern for the preservation of maritime heritage.

Municipal and Coastal Authorities

The **Comune di Anzio**, particularly the Environment Office led by **Eugenio Monaco**, has been pivotal in securing permits and navigating bureaucratic challenges. The **Demanio Marittimo**, represented by **Bruno**, offered valuable advice to avoid bureaucratic backlash. The **Capitaneria di Porto**, under **Maresciallo Constabile**, has been professional and instrumental in preparing the event space. Although the **Guardia Costiera** did not engage actively, they were kept informed.

Commercial Small Business and Hospitality Sector

Local businesses have been generally supportive of the cause. The Boat Fuel Distributor, owned by **Alberto Vecchiarelli** and operated by **Angelo Luca**, offered facilities for power and logistics. The **Bar del Porto** and **Compact One Bar** granted permission to post event information and supported the initiative. Renowned restaurants like **Capolei**, **Lampara (Cittolo)**, and **Fraschetta del Mare** have also endorsed the FishArt cause.

Beach Bathing Establishments

Local beach bathing establishments under concession, notably **Stabilimento Balneare "La Quiete"** at Marinaretti Beach, have also played an important role. They provided full support for finding young volunteers, focusing on engaging individuals in their early twenties. The involvement of "Stabilimenti Balneari" is pivotal for activating a new generation in maritime and coastal activities.

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DEL11 • Stakeholder Report

Schools and Associations

Since the first "collaboratorium," we have been in touch with several local associations such as Legambiente, Ibis Onlus, Con.Tatto, and UPublishing. Together with some of these organizations, we organized a Beach Cleanup with the support of the Comune di Anzio's Environment Department, headed by Eugenio Monaco. The Beach-Head cleanup action symbolizes a different way to commemorate the Anzio Beach-Head, a horrific battle in the Second World War that caused the loss of many young lives and remains a vivid memory among Anzio citizens.

The plogging action, titled "**Let's Not Make War, Let's Fight Waste!**" took place on the 10th of May and was a great success. It saw the participation of three schools: "**Falcone, Collodi and Acqua del Turco**", with 200 students and teachers, together with eco-activists from **Legambiente Circolo Le Rondini Anzio-Nettuno**. The local association **Raw Drivers** helped us coordinate the action and involve the schools on very short notice.

I've been told that kids who participated still play the "Eco-Warrior" game on the beach. Instead of building sandcastles, they prefer picking up waste, although it should not be their duty. Nonetheless, it works very well because adults who see them cleaning become more aware and ashamed of their behavior, making them more likely to clean up the beach after themselves.

FishArt Porto Cultura: Exploring the Sea Through Art

FishArt Porto Cultura at the Anzio Fishing Port embarks on an artistic journey exploring various perspectives of the sea and its cultural significance. This initiative aims to raise ecological awareness and inspire a deep connection with maritime traditions. Through art, the project highlights the importance of marine conservation and the impact of pollution, fostering a sense of responsibility and stewardship among visitors.

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DEL11 • Stakeholder Report

Strategies to Engage the Younger Generation

Engaging the younger generation in maritime professions and traditions is crucial for the sustainability of Anzio's maritime culture and the development of a common vision for the Anzio Seaport. FishArt Porto Cultura plays a vital role in this by integrating various strategies:

1. **Educational Programs:** Developing partnerships with local schools to incorporate maritime history, marine pollution, and practical skills into the curriculum.
2. **Youth Workshops:** Organizing workshops and hands-on activities where young people can learn about boat building, navigation, fishing techniques, and marine conservation practices.
3. **Mentorship Programs:** Pairing experienced fishermen and maritime workers with young apprentices to pass on traditional knowledge, skills, and ecological awareness.
4. **Interactive Exhibits:** Creating a series of interactive exhibits and Living Labs at the seaport to attract and educate visitors about maritime professions and the importance of marine conservation.
5. **Digital Engagement:** Utilizing social media and digital platforms to share stories, interviews, and behind-the-scenes looks at maritime life, making it more accessible and appealing to tech-savvy youth.

Conclusion

Small investments and coordinated efforts, potentially supervised by an external watchdog agency, could ensure transparency and drive results. The stakeholders of Anzio Seaport are united by a profound knowledge and passion for the sea. They are custodians of Anzio's maritime culture and are pivotal for transforming the seaport into a social space that fosters citizen participation and the development of sea-related trades and traditions. Engaging the younger generation in these professions is crucial for preserving and advancing this rich cultural heritage. The FishArt Porto Cultura initiative contributes to raising ecological awareness and fostering a deeper connection with the maritime environment through art and community engagement. Stakeholders at this stage only need a sign of recognition and someone to lead by example.

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BENEFICIARY:

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COLLABORATORS:

RAW-NEWS
report around the world

PLATOON

CULTURAL
DEVELOPMENT

**RAW
DRIVERS**

Con il Patrocinio di:

Città di Anzio

**2021
2030** United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

DIPARTIMENTO DI METODI E MODELLI
PER L'ECONOMIA IL TERRITORIO E LA FINANZA
MEMOTEF

SAPIENZA
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Work plan status vs proposed work plan

FishArt GANTT Chart

Tasks/months	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
01. Activity Management	D1		D8							
02. Communication and networking	D8	D10	D8	D10	D8, 10	D10	D8	D10	D8, 10	D8,9, 10
03. Fist workshop		D2,3 M								
04. Participatory education and training initiatives				D5	D4,5	D5 M				
05. FishArt Living Lab and Event									D6,7	M
06 Second workshop										D11 M
<i>M (milestones), D (deliverable)</i>										

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WORKPLAN

Workplan

[T.= task, m= months, sup.= support, M=milestones, Ob=objective, D=deliverables, O=Outcome, Outputs=Ou]

- T. 01 Activity Management [UniTo] (Ob1, m.1-10, CL01). Set up administrative, managerial, ethical compliance, risk and data management procedures. D: Management plans O:A-C Ou:2
- T. 02 Management of communication, networking and dissemination [UniTo, sup: media-agency] (Ob3-5, m.1-10, CL01). Set up and maintenance of web page, social media, mailing list; networking local stakeholders+target groups (fishermen and artists) and international experts, in-site communication; media contacts; photo and video documentation; scientific paper elaboration. D: 1 web page, 6 newsletters, 6 press realises, 1 scientific paper, 2 photo exhibitions (25 professional pictures) and 3 professional videos (2/3 mins), 6 YouTube videos. O:C Ou:1
- T. 03 Fist workshop [UniTo, sup: LNI] (Ob3-4, m.2, EITHE08.1). Kick-off plenary open meeting with local stakeholders and administration for process design, issue discussion, preparation and logistics for T.4 and T.5. M: FishArt local stakeholder community engaged and Implementation designed plan approved D:1 Plan for the future Harbour, Financial plan for T.3-6 O:A, B Ou:2
- T. 04 Participatory education and training initiatives [UniTo, sup: external experts] (Ob3-4, m.3-6, EITHE08.1). Preparation and realisation of collaborative education on tacit and transformative local knowledge open to all citizens (1. Transect walk with fishermen at the harbour and visiting the boats, 2. Researchers presenting the challenges for the global ocean and local area, 3. Public meeting with local schools presenting works on the society's attachment to the sea in Anzio and marine waste.) M: Matchmaking and cross-fertilisation phase for identify main challenges realised D: 1 intermediate report, 3 co-training events O:A Ou:2
- Task 05 FishArt Living Lab and Event [UniTo, sup: Fishermen coops, Platoon, Local Admin.] (Ob2&4, m.5-10, CL01). Creation of a temporary living lab with target groups and ideation of 3 artistic performances/installations, focused on marine and coastal area pollution, to be realized in the Harbour; design of the collaborative art process (involving stakeholders) and preparation of artworks (including logistic, materials and practical organisation); exhibition/exposition of the artworks during a FishArt Event at the Harbour M. Regular LL meetings and artworks practicalities arranged D. 3 artworks plan and realisation, 1 FishArt Event O:B Ou:1
- Task 06 Second workshops [UniTo] (Ob4, m.10, CL01). Plenary open meeting for results presentations, activity assessment (stakeholder survey), and design of follow-up (scaling-up and sustainability) plan. M. Survey result collected, all communication product ready, stakeholders' engagement in follow-up plan D. 1 final report including assessment and follow-up plan. O:A, B Ou:2

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wp modification

- T04_3. Public meeting with local schools presenting works on the society's attachment to the sea in Anzio and marine waste.) → realised during the LADI & the Sea event

T06_6. Change the description in "T. 03 First workshop. Kick-off plenary open meeting..." into "T. . 03 Kick-off meeting ..." and the description in "Task 06 Second workshops [UniTo] (Ob4, m.10, CL01). Plenary open meeting..." into "Task 06

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Summary of reached goals and KPIs

KPI code and name	KPI description	KPI Target value	Your contribution	Current progress (%)
KSN02	Demonstration/pilots/living labs within a project that actively involve citizens and/or local associations	200	Living Lab Sessions, Community Plogging with schools, Fishermen and citizens	Current progress (60%)
EITHE08.1	Participants in (non-degree) education and training	1	Community involvement with participation of schools, Fishermen and citizens	Current progress (70%)
CL01	Strengthened resilience to the unavoidable impacts of climate change	40	Marine Pollution sensibilisation and marine conservation divulgation	Current progress (30%)

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Any changes in project/budget?

- WORKING WITHIN THE GIVEN BUDGET
- BUDGET CHANGES: SEE TABLE PROPOSED BUDGET AND NOTES next slide
- SWITCH TRANSECT WALK TO BEACH PLOGGING ACTION
- NO CHANGES ARE PLANNED SO FAR

A. PERSONNEL	B. SUBCONTRACTING	C.1 TRAVEL AND SUBSISTENCE	C.2 EQUIPMENT	C.3 OTHER GOODS, WORKS AND SERVICES	D.1 FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO THIRD PARTIES	D.2 INTERNALLY INVOICED GOODS AND SERVICES	E. INDIRECT COSTS	Grand Total
9,981.00 €	.00 €	500.00 €	.00 €	9,500.00 €	.00 €	.00 €	4,993.00 €	24,974.00 €
9,981.00 €	.00 €	500.00 €	.00 €	9,500.00 €	.00 €	.00 €	4,993.00 €	24,974.00 €

DETAILS:

T02. Service payment for a professional media-agency to realise 1 web page, 6 newsletters, 6 press realises, 1 scientific paper, 2 photo exhibitions (25 professional pictures) and 3 professional videos (2/3 mins), 6 YouTube videos € 2500

T03. First Workshop: catering for about 40 persons and consumables (paper, pens...) - € 400

T04. Three participatory education and training initiatives: welcome drink for 50 participants in totals and consumables (paper, block notes, colors...) € 400

T05. - Materials for the realisation of three participatory artworks designed and realised by target groups in collaboration with citizens during the living lab (materials could include brushes, glue, wood, nails, ropes, photographic prints on waterproof panels, fabrics, solar lights, pedestals, stages...); Welcome drink for about 500 participants to the FishArt Event: € 5800

T06. Second Workshop: catering for about 40 persons and consumables (paper, pens...) € 400

CHANGES OPERATED:

T02 +T03+T04 +T6 ASSIGNED TO EXTERNAL SERVICE RAW- NEWS (TOTAL 4100)

T06 ASSIGNED TO PLATOON AND REDUCED TO 4900

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Looking forward: upcoming priorities and possible challenges for the rest of the project

- LIAISING WITH LOCAL AUTHORITIES
- EVENT PRODUCTION PRACTICAL CHALLENGES TO STAY WITHIN THE GIVEN BUDGET
- PROJECT MANAGEMENT PRIORITY FOR EVENT PRODUCTION
- START COMMUNICATION & PR CAMPAIGN

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DELO8 • FISHART EVENT COMMUNICATION E-FLYERS & POSTERS

FISHART
PORTO
CULTURA

27 LUGLIO
2024

MOLO
INNOCENZIANO
PORTO D'ANZIO

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PLATOON
CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT

RAW DRIVERS

LEGAMBIENTE

SEZIONE DI ANZIO

Con il contributo di:
Città di Anzio
raw-news
PLATOON
RAW DRIVERS
LEGAMBIENTE
SEZIONE DI ANZIO
DUWO

FISHART
CULTURE
SEAPORT

27 JULY
2024

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FISHART
CULTURE
SEAPORT

27 JULY
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DUWO

Expected & unexpected challenges and how they have been addressed

FISHART EVENT PLANNING AND PRODUCTION HAS BEEN CHALLENGING AT TIMES:

- WAITING FOR MEETING WITH TECHNICIANS FOR ELECTRICITY
- NEED CONFIRMATION FROM PORT AUTHORITIES TO BLOCK TRAFFIC AND PARKING IN FRONT OF THE AREA
- ALL DOCUMENTS HAVE BEEN SENT TO ALL RELEVANT AUTHORITIES
- HEALTH & SAFETY PLAN: FIRE EXTINGUISHERS AND SECURITY TEAM
- TEST SETUP PLANNED FOR WEEK BEFORE THE EVENT

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EVENT PROGRAM	STATUS	EXAMPLE	TYPE	GENRE	WEB
DADARA	CONFIRMED	https://dadara.nl/art/transformoney-tree	INSTALLATION	PARTICIPATORY ART	https://dadara.nl/
CRISTIANO CESOLARI	CONFIRMED	IMPOSSIBLE LANDSCAPE - NEKTON	IMMERSIVE	AV & DIGITAL	https://www.instagram.com/lotoprod
PERERA ELSEWHERE	CONFIRMED		PERFORMANCE	MUSIC	https://www.pereraelsewhere.com/
EMAILA KANGUDIE	CONFIRMED				
JOE VANGELI	CONFIRMED		PERFORMANCE	MUSIC	https://www.mixcloud.com/joevangelidj/
GIUSEPPE LUPINACCI	CONFIRMED		PHOTO EXHIBITION	PHOTOGRAPHY	https://www.instagram.com/lupinacci_giuseppe/
ILARIA KANGUDIE	CONFIRMED	Acrobatic Performers	PERFORMANCE	ACROBATIC	
ALESSANDRA DI COLA	CONFIRMED	ALMA CREAZ BEACH ARTCRAFTS	BEACH MEMORIES	ARTCRAFT	https://www.facebook.com/alma.creazione
OPEN CALL PROPOSALS					
LAURA BUFFA	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	SCULPTURE	ART	https://www.laurabuffaonline.com/laura-buffa
MARTINA TROIANO	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	SCULPTURE	ART	https://www.facebook.com/artalo.lab/
ROBERTA FUCCI	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	ILLUSTRATIONS COMICS	ART	http://robertafucci.online/
ROMOLO BASILI	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	SCULPTURE	INTELLIGENZA ARTIGIANALE	https://www.instagram.com/romolo.basili/
IBIS • ANNASERRA FRANCO	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	FISHNET LABIRYNTH	ART INSTALLATION	http://www.ibisonlus.com/
GIOVANNI LUPI	TBC	PROPOSAL Proposta provocatoria	PERFORMANCE	PROVOCATION	https://www.youtube.com/@giovannilupi1/videos
Aps Con_tatto , Ass. culturale UPublishing	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	WORKSHOP	BOOK CROSSING	https://www.instagram.com/aps_con_tatto/
LEGAMBIENTE	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	WORKSHOP	CREATIVE LAB	https://legambienteazio.it/
ILARIA PACCINI	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	EXHIBITION	PAINTING	https://www.facebook.com/romaspeciale
BIANCA SIMONETTI	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	PHOTO EXHIBITION	PHOTOGRAPHY	https://biankayeahmo.wixsite.com/photo
JIMLEA NADEZHDA MENDOZA	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	ILLUSTRATION PANELS	SCIENCE RESEARCH	
PATRIZIA FERRANDES	CONFIRMED	PROPOSAL	ILLUSTRATION PANELS	SCIENCE RESEARCH	

PARTICIPATORY ART PROGRAM

ARTIST, CREATIVES,
ENVIRONMENT ENTHUSIASTS
FOR THE CREATION OF
ARTWORKS

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FISHART EVENT	27 JULY TIMELINE
SETUP	
7:00	Meetup Molo Innocenziano, Setup Equipment, Briefing Workplan
8:00	Setup Fishnet Labirynt (Team 1)
9:00	Setup Co-Creation Stations (Tables, Seats & Modular Furniture (Team 2)
10:00	Setup Info Panels, Fine Tune & Tech Check (Team 3)
12:00	Lunch Break
14:00	Beach Siesta
16:00	Meetup at Culture Seaport - Exhibition Participants arrive and set up their artworks
START	
17:00	Beginning of the event in collaboration with local associations, volunteers, fishermen, young talents, and creatives.
18:00 - 20:30	Open co-creation workshop for everyone. Includes:
18:30	- Creating artifacts with recovered marine plastics.
	- Displaying the works in the Marine Trash Museum.
	- Marine Pollution Catalog: Citizen Science.
	- Readings, installations and performances
19:00	- Fresh Trash Market - FishPlastic Market Performance
	-Exhibition and exchange of artistic creations made with marine waste.
19:00	- Sound Waves exploring marine themes through low-frequency sound waves and underwater sounds.
20:30	Sunset Live set by Perera Elsewhere at sunset, a musical experience in the FishArt labyrinth
23:30	- After the music ends, socializing continues at the Cultural Seaport, with spontaneous performances.
23:00	Team dismantles equipment and cleans. Fishnets stay until the day after.

WHEN	WHAT	WHO	WHERE	ROLE	TYPE
01.06.2024	MEETING PLATOON	Marcello, Christoph Frank	Marquede	Project Management	MANAGEMENT
02.06.2024	MEETING PLATOON	Marcello, Christoph Frank	Marquede	Curation	PROGRAM
02.06.2024	MEETING RAW DRIVERS	Marcello, Francesca, Valeria, Vinz	Online	Curator	CURATION
03.06.2024	MEETING PLATOON	Marcello, Christoph Frank	Marquede	Event Production	PRODUCTION
06.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Sasha Perera	Berlin	Artist	PROGRAM
07.06.2024	MEETING SAFETY PLAN	Marcello, Stella	Berlin	Achitect	MANAGEMENT
09.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Cristiano Cesolari	Berlin	Artist	PROGRAM
10.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Francesca	Rome	Curator	MANAGEMENT
11.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Dadara	Online	Artist	PROGRAM
12.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Giuseppe Lupinacci	Molo Innocenziano	Artist	PROGRAM
12.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Fede, Emá, Marco, Kris, Vale, Giuseppe	Babylon Pizzeria	Construction	PRODUCTION
13.06.2024	LOCATION CHECK	Marcello, Fede, Emá	Molo Innocenziano	Construction	PRODUCTION
13.06.2024	MATERIAL & TOOLS	Marcello, Fede, Emá	Lega Navale	Construction	PRODUCTION
14.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Fede	Molo Innocenziano	Setup	PRODUCTION
15.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Fede, Emá, Valeria	Anzio House	Setup	PRODUCTION
16.06.2024	MEETING PRODUCTION	Marcello, Fede, Vale, Francesca, Biondo, Emá, Fulvio	Beach Meetup	Setup	PRODUCTION
16.06.2024	MEETING CURATION	Marcello, Raw Drivers	Ohana	Curation	PROGRAM
17.06.2024	MEETING COMUNE	Marcello, Monaco, Fede	Molo Innocenziano	Permits	MANAGEMENT
17.06.2024	PRODUCTION TASKS	Marcello, Marco, Krish, Fede, Emá	Anzio House	Sound System	PRODUCTION
17.06.2024	MEETING SUPPORTERS	Marcello, Pasquale SinEco, Marco D.	Romolo al Porto	Recycling	PRODUCTION
18.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Marco, Krish	Anzio House	Sound System	PRODUCTION
19.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Lucia Martino	Marinaretti	Coordinator	PRODUCTION
19.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Giuseppe Lupinacci & Fede	Fraschetta del Mare	Artist	PROGRAM
20.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, IBIS, Fede	Anzio House	Artist	PROGRAM
20.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Ilaria Paccini	Molo Innocenziano	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING FISHERMEN	Angelo, Fede, Marcello	Molo Innocenziano	Fisherman	PRODUCTION
21.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Chiara	Online	Project Lead	MANAGEMENT
21.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Valeria, Fede	Beach Meetup	Setup	PRODUCTION
21.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Ilaria Acrobats	Anzio House	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Emaila Vocalist	Anzio House	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Alessandra di Cola - AlmaCreaz	Approdo	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING RAW DRIVERS	Marcello, Isa, Fede, Emá, Vale, Laura	Approdo	Curator	PROGRAM
22.06.2024	MEETING TECHNICIANS	Marcello, Marco, Cesare, Paolo	Anzio House	Sound Engineer	PRODUCTION
23.06.2024	MEETING MATERIALS	Marcello, Ema, Pasquale SinEcoMarcello,	SinEco	Recycling plant	PRODUCTION
24.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Chiara			REPORT
25.06.2024	MEETING COMUNE	Marcello			MANAGEMENT
26.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Cristiano Cesolari	Lotoprod	Artist	PROGRAM
28.06.2024	MIDTERM REPORT	Marcello			MANAGEMENT
28.06.2024	DESIGN POSTERS	Marcello			PRODUCTION
29.06.2024	LIVING LAB	Legambiente, Con.Tatto, Uplishing, Raw Drivers, Dalia, Bianca, Roberta, Jimlea, Marcello, Chiara, Fede, Giuseppe		Participants	PROGRAM
30.06.2024	MIDTERM REPORT	Marcello, Chiara, Laura			MANAGEMENT

DEL01 • MEETINGS & WORK SESSIONS

- [PROJECT MANAGEMENT WORKFLOW](#)

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Space to add photos/evidence of success

Visual Review and evidence of success

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